

Farmer Clusters: A great networking opportunity for a biodiverse and prosperous Monte Pisano

Policy recommendations

In marginal rural areas like the Monte Pisano olive agroecosystem, the formation and coordination of a Farmer Cluster (FC) by a local FC Facilitator, has been proven an effective approach to increase awareness among farmers and citizens about the relevance of olive systems in sustaining the local biodiversity, about the agro-environmental vulnerability of the Monte Pisano area, and to create cohesion among local stakeholders all aiming at safeguarding the local socio-economic system. Discussions during the final project event resulted in the following policy recommendations:

- **Invest in long-term facilitation and support.** Government and rural development policies should embed training, resourcing, and financing for Farmer Cluster facilitators as core elements of agri-environmental programmes. By supporting skilled facilitators to build trust, coordinate activity, and link farmers to external expertise and innovations from research, co-designed local policies could enable Farmer Clusters to deliver long-term benefits for biodiversity and rural communities. In some cases, like Monte Pisano, an enlarged farmer cluster should be envisaged including all value chain actors to achieve impact.
- **Enhance cohesion among local value chain actors.** Producing olive oil involves a series of local actors that all need to be aligned to create a recognisable market for final consumers. It includes producers, millers, retailers and consumers. Producers may have different market objectives and millers need to be able to respond to all of them. To maintain an economically sound local production chain, local policies are needed to support the multiple objectives of all the actors involved. Farmer Clusters can be a sound starting point to create cohesions and dialogue among all local actors.
- **Enhance Payments for Ecosystem Services (PES).** Policy should support PES especially in areas that are environmentally vulnerable but that have a high natural value including biodiversity. In these areas, the value of farming is not only for food production, but sustainable farming practices contribute significantly to provide geohydrological security, biodiversity maintenance and local economies. These ecosystem services can never be paid by the products alone and well-designed PES can help to pay farmers for these, so far, unpaid and not recognised services.
- **Citizens awareness about Ecosystem Services provided by agriculture in marginal areas.** Policy makers and municipalities should support and finance BioBlitz activities as a way to increase citizens awareness about the biodiversity and ecosystem services provided by agricultural in marginal areas. This may have snowball effect on citizens willingness to pay for ecosystem services.

Transformative impact of Farmer Clusters on farmland biodiversity and local value chain cohesion

In many areas farmland biodiversity is in decline, threatening both agroecosystem services and long-term food system resilience. In the majority of areas this is due to intensive farming practices that destroy semi-natural habitats and cause pollution and eutrofication of the environment, thus impacting plant and animal coenoses that rely on low disturbance levels, and low soil fertility.

Furthermore, these highly intensive systems rely to a great extent on pesticides that reduce diverse plant, insect and bird communities, affecting the entire foodchain.

Much less attention is paid to biodiversity losses in the marginal farming areas, that cannot apply intensive farming practices due to the local soil, geohydrological or climatic conditions. In most of the marginal areas, more and more farmers give up, resulting in land abandonment. The MIDAS EU Project (<https://www.midas-bioeconomy.eu/news/mapping-the-extent-of-marginal-land-in-europe/>) estimates that about 29% of the EU28 agricultural land can be classified as marginal land. Land abandonment results in unguided renaturalisation and the question remains if these new areas provide more or less ecosystem services than the low-input farming systems that were in place before. The FRAMEwork project investigated the impact on biodiversity of some key groups in and around abandoned land. Focus groups, organised by the local Farmer Cluster Facilitator, identified the ecosystem services provided by these low-input farming systems as perceived by a wide variety of local stakeholders. Having Farmer Clusters with a FC Facilitator, can therefore support communication and knowledge exchange between all the local stakeholder groups and this can generate common decisions and action plans supported by the local community. This can be of great interest and support for local policy makers as a starting point for innovative and efficient rural development and CAP policies.

Approach and results

The EU Horizon 2020 project FRAMEwork and in particular three Farmer Clusters, decided to investigate the effect of land abandonment on biodiversity. Three cropping systems were involved: arable land in Estonia, Alpine grassland in Austria and a terraced olive grove system in Italy. Biodiversity was monitored in abandoned fields, in the cropped fields adjacent to the abandoned ones, and in cropped fields at 1 km distance from abandoned land. Beneficial insects, key pests and species of conservation interest were monitored. Although different groups of insects had opposite responses or were not affected by land abandonment, overall, it was shown that beneficial insects for pest control, were more often negatively affected by land abandonment, therefore decreasing the conservation biological control potential in adjacent cropped fields. This effect was particularly strong in the Monte Pisano case study, for staphylinid beetles and carabids, two well-known predator groups of the larvae of the olive fruit fly.

Focus groups were held with local stakeholders discussing causes of land abandonment, connected risks and potential solutions. In all three cases, land abandonment was perceived especially as a socio-economic risk and decline, farmers felt left alone by society and policy makers, and they feel that support for their low-input farming systems would generate benefits for ecosystem service provisioning. This type of farming is not perceived as a threat to biodiversity, and on the contrary, low-input farming enriches land use diversity and plant and insect species communities.

Good farming practices and the ecosystem services they provide

In the case of the Italian Farmer Cluster, we experienced some reluctance from farmers with different lifestyles and viewpoints to collaborate. However, by the end of the project, the FC evolved towards an enlarged Cluster including other value chain actors who recognise the importance of the olive oil

value chain to sustain the Monte Pisano agroecosystem and work towards sustainable local development goals. In this case study, biodiversity conservation can only be achieved through durable and sustainable olive oil value chains allowing farmers to produce using sustainable, low input farming practices and receiving support for landscape maintenance. Support needs to be found for dedicated mowing regimes, wildfire control, maintenance of the dry stonewall geo-hydrological system and sustainable pruning and olive collection systems. Furthermore, the continuous fight against the olive fruit fly requires landscape scale solutions, and this is widely recognised by all farmers. During the final Cluster event local stakeholders identified four farming practices that were considered most relevant for ecosystem service provisioning, and they indicated which services are expected to benefit.

- **Mowing regime**

There is a strong need and obligation to mow the herbaceous vegetation covering the olive groves. This is mainly due to wildfire control in summer, and the need to have a clean understorey at the time of olive harvesting, which is done by putting nets on the ground. However, differential mowing can be practiced by always leaving some flowering patches for insects and allow plant species to set seed.

- **Rotational grazing of sheep**

Inclusion of sheep in the system supports soil fertility and alleviates complications with mowing. It offers opportunity to have extra income from pecorino cheese production. Care needs to be taken with erosion and dry stonewall damage due to overgrazing. Choice of animal race is fundamental for the success.

- **Maintenance of dry-stone walls and drainage channels**

This is a fundamental activity for geohydrological stability of the entire Mountain system. This service provides benefits to the entire region. The cost of maintenance and restoration is extremely high and for earth-retaining walls it can vary from 150 to over 200 euro per square meter. The stone walls offer an exclusive habitat for plant species, insects and reptiles, beside increasing the attractivity of the area.

- **Beekeeping**

Honeybees support pollination of wild plant species and therewith they sustain the entire trophic chain. Honey production provides an extra income to farmers and it generally promotes the rural economy and ecotourism.

Good farming practices related to olive pruning, burning/chopping of pruning material and olive collection are very important practices that are less directly related to biodiversity management. These issues were not explored in detail. However, the impact on carbon footprint can be strong and therefore they can be relevant for PES as well. Non-chemical methods for olive fruit fly control are another issue strongly debated in the Monte Pisano region, but this is deeply explored in the IPMWork project. Most farmers on the Mountain are growing organically, even if not always certified.

Policy implications

It became evident during the 5 years of the project and all interactions with local olive growers and value chain actors that farmers strongly feel there is a private economic burden on their shoulders

while there is a clear collective benefit deriving from their investments and efforts. Proper olive grove management is expensive in this terraced landscape, while the environmental benefits are enjoyed by the broader community. Meanwhile, production revenues do not cover the costs. The focus group on land abandonment in the Monte Pisano area offered an interesting potential solution: development of a system allowing to support farmers through Payments for Ecosystem Services (PES). This option was further developed and discussed during the final event and the following findings were reported by the working group:

- All participants declared to be **in favour of PES in the local area**. Some participants specified that they would only be so if the commitment is for at least 5 years and the PES approach was not merely anthropocentric but conservationist (protection of habitats and rare species).
- Participants agreed that **olive growers should be considered landscape stewards**. Olive growers play a key role in preserving the landscape and delivering essential ecosystem services, such as preventing erosion and protecting biodiversity. While the proper maintenance of olive groves benefits the wider community by reducing environmental risks downstream, it often provides little or no direct economic return for the farmers themselves. They deserve fair economic recognition.
- Olive growers need structural support and accountability of their efforts. They should receive structured payments for sustainable land management, possibly combined with carbon credits. To this end, it is hypothesized to set up a system with a list of good practices and the respective ecosystem services they provide. Each olive grower in the area can determine which services and practices are most relevant in his/her context and adhere to the PES system indicating the farming practices/ecosystem services they ask support for.

Concerning who should/could deliver payments, the following entities were identified:

- tourists (extra minimum tax for those visiting the territory);
- public institutions (regional administrative authority);
- private entities (through the support of public administrations that could provide tax relief);
- local community (not all participants agreed on this point).

To conclude, the FRAMEwork project showed that monitoring is vital for understanding the effectiveness of conservation measures and motivate farmers and consumers. Monitoring of ecosystem service delivery and biodiversity can strongly motivate people to support PES. Throughout the project, citizen science initiatives—particularly the BioBlitz—have played a key role in raising awareness about the biodiversity present in low-input olive grove systems and the efforts required to sustain it. In the Monte Pisano area, several municipalities have already recognized the value of these activities and began to support the organisation of the Monte Pisano BioBlitz. This can provide a strong support for the development of an efficient PES system and facilitate the uptake of PES. Local municipalities are therefore invited to become more active in sustaining and financing BioBlitz activities.

These proposals are preliminary, but there was a very strong support from the local community. We, therefore, call on local policy makers to contact us to establish a road map to further explore this opportunity. As a concluding note, we add that a similar approach has been proposed for woodland management. Issues and management practices are different, but similarities can be found, and this system can provide a strong basis for the olive grove PES system with farmers as key beneficiaries.

References / Further Reading

Bohnet, I., Thomas, F., Zagata, L., Hardy, C., Fritschle, M., Engel, S., & Kuhfuss, L. (2025). D6.1 Report on the impact of Cluster approach on Farmer's self-identity and behaviour (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15090426>).

To learn more about the FRAMEwork eleven Farmer Cluster, see <https://recodo.io/page/farmer-clusters/farmer-cluster-finder>.

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